

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17977856

CULTURAL VALUES ARCHETYPES AS DRIVERS OF FIRM PERFORMANCE: EXPLORING THE INTERPLAY OF EMPLOYEE BEHAVIOR AND DIGITAL LEADERSHIP

Mohanad Mohammed Sufyan Ghaleb^{1*}, Chok Nyen Vui²

¹*Department of Management, School of Business, King Faisal University, Al-Ahsa 31982, Saudi Arabia*

²*Department: Chancellor Office, Meritus University, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.*

Received: 18/07/2025

Accepted: 30/10/2025

Corresponding author: Mohanad Mohammed Sufyan Ghaleb

(mghaleb@kfu.edu.sa)

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the linkages among cultural identity, cultural tendency, place attachment, and destination loyalty in the heritage tourism context. The research explores how cultural identity affects tourists' cultural tendency and subsequently their destination loyalty. The study further investigates the mediating effect of cultural tendency and moderating influences of place attachment and cultural heritage awareness on these linkages. A quantitative study design was utilized, with information gathered from 212 tourists at different heritage sites. A pre-tested questionnaire based on validated scales in earlier research was utilized to assess crucial constructs. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using ADANCO was used to analyze the data, ensuring rigorous examination of direct, mediating, and moderating effects in the conceptual framework proposed. The findings support the fact that cultural identity has a positive effect on cultural tendency, hence boosting destination loyalty. Cultural tendency mediates the relationship between cultural identity and destination loyalty. Furthermore, place attachment enhances the relationship between cultural identity and cultural tendency, whereas cultural heritage awareness positively moderates the influence of cultural tendency on destination loyalty. This research adds to heritage tourism literature with empirical evidence on psychological and cultural factors that affect destination loyalty. The results yield practical recommendations for tourism policymakers and marketers to create culturally engaging activities that maximize tourist involvement and affinity.

KEYWORDS: Cultural Identity, Cultural Tendency, Destination Loyalty, Heritage Tourism, Place Attachment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are widely recognized as critical drivers of economic growth, innovation, and employment across the globe (Gherghina et al., 2020; Joo et al., 2025). Despite their importance, SMEs often face significant challenges in maintaining competitiveness and sustaining performance in dynamic and uncertain business environments (Youssef & ElSabry, 2025). Organizational culture is created through the shared belief systems, values, and norms common to all members within an organization. Organizational culture is also regarded as a critical asset to employees as it can influence their choices and the outcomes of their organizations. In defining organizational culture, several cultural value archetypes illustrate the way an employee perceives about job role, makes decisions, and contributes to the goals of the organization. The relationship between the cultural value archetypes and the employee behavior has particular relevance for SMEs (Ababneh, 2021) since the limited resources and small structure of SMEs means that employee behaviors and alignment with the cultural values will have a more significant influence on the overall success of the business.

Practically, SMEs frequently struggle to achieve consistent firm performance due to insufficiently engaged or misaligned employees. Many organizations spend considerable amounts of money and build structures (Delmotte et al., 2006; Kmecová & Androniceanu, 2024), however most organizations do not recognize that a large number of organizations productivity and innovation challenges are behavioral or cultural in nature. Behaviors that drive employee behavior (e.g., initiative, cooperative behavior, creative problem-solving, accountability) have a direct impact on operational efficiency and value. In SMEs, where every employee plays such an important part in bringing value to the organization (Kharub et al., 2025), employees exhibiting less-than-optimal behaviors have an even greater negative impact on the growth and competitive advantage of organizations. Therefore, this situation creates a practical issue that warrants further study of employee behavioral characteristics and the development of improvement opportunities for employee performance and, ultimately, for the performance of the organization.

Theoretically, although prior research has emphasized the link between organizational culture, employee behavior, and performance (Bindel Sibassaha et al., 2025; Cherian et al., 2021; Iqbal & Parray, 2025), significant gaps remain, specifically in the context of SMEs. Many previous studies have primarily looked at large organizations (Isac et al.,

2021; Putthiwani, 2015), where the size of the organization and its resources such as formal policies, procedures and structures are likely to limit the impact that culture has on the behaviors of employees. Less attention has also been given to the fact that digital leadership can serve as a strategic capability that can impact organization performance directly and can moderate the effectiveness of employee behavior. These gaps highlight the need for a new framework that integrates cultural archetypes, employee behaviors, and digital leadership to identify the performance outcomes of smaller, resource-constrained organizations more thoroughly.

The objective of this study is to examine the influence of cultural values archetypes on firm performance through employee behavior in SMEs. Additionally, the study examines how digital leadership has an influence on employee performance and subsequently has an impact on business outcomes in terms of performance. It improves the understanding of dynamic capabilities and organizational cultures within SMEs. Through empirical findings, this research illustrates how internal resources can be converted into measurable outcomes for SMEs. Moreover, this research highlights the importance of leadership in an increasingly digital environment. The primary value of the findings will provide an opportunity for SME managers and policymakers to gain insights about how to effectively manage their SMEs through innovative means. This study seeks to provide stakeholders with an overview of how to utilize technology strategically to improve employee productivity and gain a competitive advantage in their respective industries. In this research, we have identified many of the factors and characteristics necessary for digital leadership. This study is designed to provide the appropriate tools to assist digital leaders of SMEs in creating a culture around digital readiness of their employees to provide them with the ability to grow as leaders in their organizations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) explains how firms achieve superior performance by building, integrating, and reconfiguring organizational resources in rapidly varying environments (Teece et al., 1997) which is consistent with the current study. The four primary internal capabilities of the business are referred to as cultural value archetypes and, therefore, define how to find and obtain opportunities through employee actions leading to continual business improvement. As such, employee action is a behavioral representation of the organization's dynamic

capabilities, allowing for the firm to convert the organizational cultural strengths into superior performance (Januszkiewicz, 2022). Digital leadership is the capacity to lead a company in using technology, managing digital initiatives, and helping employees adapt to change (Shin et al., 2023; Wijaya et al., 2025). Digital leadership not only drives performance for a company directly but also helps improve how employee performance is connected to overall company performance (Benitez et al., 2022). Therefore, the theory of dynamic capabilities effectively explains how cultural archetypes and leadership work together to enable companies to adapt, innovate, and produce sustained performance results. This study proposed the relationship between cultural value archetypes such as innovation culture, goals culture, norms culture and digital culture along with employee behavior based on DCT which is reported in Figure 1.

2.1. Cultural Values Archetypes and Employee Behavior

This study considered cultural values archetypes through four dimensions such as innovation culture, goals culture, norms culture and digital culture. An innovation culture indicates that organizations are committed to creative expression, experimentation, and improving continuously (Al Koliby et al., 2024). At the time when organizations host employees in an advanced culture, employees are consequently fostered to show initiative by generating new ideas, taking risks to achieve those ideas, and creating solutions to problems. Employees in innovative cultures have greater agility (Zhang et al., 2022) than employees within their organizations due to dynamic capabilities theory (Bierkowska & Tworek, 2020) that supports innovative cultural values. This agility allows employees to sense opportunities and act in the right direction in the interest of company (Xiufan & Yunqiao, 2025). Therefore, innovation culture delivers the motivational and structural environment necessary for employees to provide positive and high-performance-related behaviors in their roles.

Hypothesis 1 (H1): There is a positive relationship between innovation culture and employee behavior.

A culture of goal-oriented objectives, defined performance standards, and anticipated outcomes in every aspect of employee job and the organization as a whole (Januszkiewicz, 2022). Having a clear definition of common goals aids employees in creating their direction and purpose for performing their job functions. This clarity also promotes responsible behavior and decision-making (Liu et al., 2019) by giving employees guidance on how they approach their daily tasks as well as establishing the basis of how

each employee prioritizes individual responsibilities. It also aligns their organization with organizational goals, thereby fulfilling those responsibilities within the confines of organizational standards established for all employees. Therefore, culture of the organization has vital relationship with employee behavior (Suharto & Nusantoro, 2018; Zheng et al., 2017). A clear identification of their contributions to the complete success of the organization leads to increased levels of disciplined, committed, and achievement-oriented employee behavior, and therefore greater positive and stronger employee behavior.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): There is a positive relationship between goals culture and employee behavior.

Cultural norms are the shared expectations, behavioral standards, and unwritten rules form the basis for creating a "culture" of norms that govern how an organization employees perform their jobs on a day-to-day basis (Canning et al., 2020). Norms within the organization enhance predictable workplace where managers and employees know what type of behavior can be acceptable and desirable (Oude Mulders et al., 2017). Strongly held and understood cultural norms can enhance employee cooperation, organizational responsibility, ethical decision-making, and devotion to organizational values. Cultural norms also provide frameworks through which employees can build a set of "behavioral intention" within an organization (Meng et al., 2022). Using the DCT framework (Zotoo et al., 2021), cultural norms are viewed as behavioral routines that facilitate coordinated action and provide employees with confidence which helps the employees to respond towards organizational requirements. Sometimes, when an organizational employee perceives its cultural norms to be "fair," with the objectives and values of organization, they likely to adopt those norms as an internalized part of their own behaviors, demonstrating positive behaviors in a compliant and cooperative manner. Therefore, norms culture contributes positively to the employee's behavior.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): There is a positive relationship between norms culture and employee behavior.

Digital culture of an organization is willingness to adopt and integrate the use of digital technology into their regular work (Proksch et al., 2024). Organizations promotes a digital openness culture (Lamberti et al., 2025; Mihelj et al., 2019), it provides its employees with a collaborative learning experience while also encouraging the use of technology (Fabbri et al., 2019). This enables employees to develop digital skills and modify their behavior such that the employees can utilize their technology tools effectively (Cabrero et al., 2021).

Cultural Values Archetypes

Figure 1: Framework of the Study

A strong digital culture encourages experimentation with digital solutions which help the employee in decision making (Rab, 2007). Therefore, employees who work in a digital culture perform with more innovative, adaptable and efficient behavior.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): There is a positive relationship between digital culture and employee behavior.

2.2. Employee Behavior and Firm Performance

Employee behavior is most significant factor which has effect on company ability to generate revenue (Sharif et al., 2022). Proactivity and commitment from employees have a direct effect on the company capability to operate efficiently (Joo & Bennett III, 2018), deliver high-quality services (Lau et al., 2017; Mikic Little & Dean, 2006) and adapt quickly to changing circumstances. The more employees are engaged in collaboration, problem-solving, taking initiative, and being accountable for their work (Chlpeková et al., 2014), the better able to create, deliver and communicate value to both external and internal stakeholders. By engaging in high-quality employee behavioral contributions that align with and support the goals of the organization, companies are better able to generate higher levels of productivity, greater customer satisfaction, and ultimately achieve superior performance outcomes.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): There is a positive relationship between employee behavior and firm performance.

2.3. Moderating role of Digital Leadership between Employee Behavior and Firm Performance

Digital leadership has invented as a critical strategic capability that shapes how organizations navigate technological change, align digital initiatives, and enhance performance outcomes (Khaw et al., 2022). Organizations that have an effective digital vision, an excellent understanding of technology help to communicate well using change-

oriented communication which has the potential to create a culture that is supportive of digital tools and data driven practices. Therefore, in turn, creating an organization with improved efficiency, innovation, and overall firm performance (Artüz & Bayraktar, 2021). A strong digital vision, strong understanding of technology, and the use of change-oriented communication; establish an environment to enable the use of digital tools as well as data-driven practices leading to improve efficiency, innovation and overall firm performance. Digital leadership has a direct effect on employee behavioral mechanisms (Gao & Gao, 2024; Yang et al., 2025) that create value in terms of performance through providing digital support and clarity. It helps in inspiring employees to be confident using technology and motivating employees to be productive with their skills (Wijaya et al., 2019). Therefore, digital leadership moderates the relationship between employee behavior and firm performance which allows organizations to obtain more value and enhance dynamic digital environments.

Hypothesis 6 (H6): There is a positive relationship between digital leadership and firm performance.

Hypothesis 7 (H7): Digital leadership positively moderates the relationship between employee behavior and firm performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

The selection of SMEs for this research is based upon their importance as a group of businesses that are primary components of current economy of the country. However, this sector is also very sensitive to change within technology, culture, and organization. SMEs tend to have various limitations in terms of resources, capability gaps, and therefore tend to perform worse than their larger competitors due to more exposure to internal and external stressors. Therefore, considering the strategic practices and

emerging technologies used within the SME sector can further promote innovation, flexibility, and effective utilization of resources are necessary for continued growth and development.

To address the performance of SMEs, this study considered the relationship between innovation culture, goals culture, norms culture and digital culture along with employee behavior based on DCT. This relationship is tested with the help of **quantitative research approach**. A survey questionnaire was employed as the primary data collection instrument, enabling the systematic measurement of constructs and testing of hypotheses. This questionnaire used only validated scales from previous studies which are adapted to the context of SMEs and was created in sections measuring the constructs: innovation culture, goals culture, norms culture, digital culture, employee behavior, digital leadership, and firm performance. A 5-point Likert scale was used in this study to record the perceptions and experiences of respondents, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree".

The target population for this study comprised employees working in SMEs across various industries, including manufacturing, services, and technology. Employees were chosen for selection based on their direct impact on the organizational culture, involvement in daily operational functions, and contribution to overall business performance. The employees were selected using a simple random sampling technique to ensure adequate experience and familiarity with organizational leadership and culture practices. To ensure that employees are sufficiently familiar with their organizational behavioral and operational standards, only employees who have been with the organization for a minimum of 1 year were selected as potential participants.

The data collection process involved distributing the survey both online and self-visit to maximize

reach and response rate. Respondents were guaranteed privacy as well as anonymity to boost honest and accurate responses. Prior to full-scale distribution, a pilot study was performed with 30 employees to assess the reliability and validity of the questionnaire items. Based on pilot feedback, minor modifications were made to advance item wording and comprehensibility. Two hundred and twenty-one (221) valid responses were received. Four dimensions of cultural value archetypes such as innovation culture, goals culture, norms culture and digital culture was measured by adapting scale items from (Leal-Rodríguez et al., 2023). Five scale items were used to measure employee behavior, adapted from Leal-Rodríguez et al. (2023). Six scale items were used to measure digital leadership and five scale items were used to measure firm performance, adapted from (Shin et al., 2023).

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 1 highlighted the demographic profile of respondents. The demographic profile shows that most SME respondents are **male (77.83%)**, with females representing **22.17%** of the sample. It shows that most of the employees working in SMEs are males as compared to the females. Most participants fall within the **26–35 age group (45.70%)**, indicating young as well as active workforce typical of SME environments. Hence, most of the employees working in SMEs are young. A significant proportion of respondents hold **master degrees (43.89%)**, reflecting strong educational backgrounds within the sector. Furthermore, most of respondents have significant work experience for those who participated in the study. Work experience is widely distributed, with the largest segment having **1–3 years of experience (32.13%)**, followed closely by those with **4–6 years (31.22%)**.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Category	Sub-Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	172	77.83%
	Female	49	22.17%
Age	18–25 years	42	19.00%
	26–35 years	101	45.70%
	36–45 years	52	23.53%
	Above 45 years	26	11.76%
Education	Bachelor's	79	35.75%
	Master's	97	43.89%
	MPhil/MS	30	13.57%
	PhD	15	6.79%
Experience	Less than 1 year	24	10.86%
	1–3 years	71	32.13%
	4–6 years	69	31.22%
	Above 6 years	57	25.79%

4.2. Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)

Measurement model was used to explore the individual item reliability, construct reliability and validity (García-Fernández et al., 2018; Hair et al., 2012; Henseler et al., 2009). The measurement model shows strong reliability as well as validity across all constructs. The lowest and highest loading of scale items are 0.769 and 0.937 respectively. The internal consistency of all constructs is satisfactory with Cronbach Alpha which is greater than 0.90 and composite reliability is greater than 0.94, both exceeding the minimum recommended values (Cheah et al., 2018; Henseler et al., 2014). The average

variance extracted (AVE) values are all greater than 0.50, confirming that there is a satisfactory level of convergent validity across all constructs (Anis et al., 2020; Cheah et al., 2018). Therefore, the measurement model is robust, reliable, and valid for measuring the connection between digital culture, digital leadership, employee behaviors, firm performance, cultural goals, innovation culture and norms culture. Moreover, discriminant validity is reported in Table 2 by using AVE square root. To determine construct discriminant validity, square root of AVE is verified in SEM and confirmatory factor analysis. Building on Fornell-Larcker guidelines, the square root of AVE for all constructs needs to exceed correlations between those constructs (Hilkenmeier et al., 2020).

Table 2: Factor Loadings, Alpha, Composite Reliability and AVE

Construct	Items	Loading	Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Digital Culture	DC1	0.936	0.966	0.972	0.854
	DC2	0.925			
	DC3	0.908			
	DC4	0.928			
	DC5	0.922			
	DC6	0.925			
Digital Leadership	DL3	0.919	0.945	0.961	0.859
	DL4	0.934			
	DL5	0.921			
	DL6	0.933			
Employee Behavior	EB1	0.937	0.956	0.966	0.85
	EB2	0.921			
	EB3	0.931			
	EB4	0.896			
	EB5	0.924			
Firm Performance	FP1	0.909	0.945	0.958	0.819
	FP2	0.901			
	FP3	0.907			
	FP4	0.884			
	FP5	0.925			
Goals Culture	GC1	0.868	0.952	0.961	0.806
	GC2	0.913			
	GC3	0.869			
	GC4	0.903			
	GC5	0.908			
	GC6	0.922			
Innovation Culture	IC1	0.91	0.951	0.961	0.802
	IC2	0.922			
	IC3	0.913			
	IC4	0.875			
	IC5	0.889			
	IC6	0.864			
Norms Culture	NC1	0.77	0.924	0.94	0.725
	NC2	0.769			
	NC3	0.867			
	NC4	0.898			
	NC5	0.918			
	NC6	0.873			

Table 3: AVE Square Root

	Digital Culture	Digital Leadership	Employee Behavior	Firm Performance	Goals Culture	Innovation Culture	Norms Culture
Digital Culture	0.924						
Digital Leadership	0.452	0.927					
Employee Behavior	0.851	0.471	0.922				

Table 3: AVE Square Root (cont...)

	Digital Culture	Digital Leadership	Employee Behavior	Firm Performance	Goals Culture	Innovation Culture	Norms Culture
Firm Performance	0.434	0.636	0.445	0.905			
Goals Culture	0.649	0.426	0.642	0.42	0.898		
Innovation Culture	0.689	0.404	0.674	0.396	0.625	0.896	
Norms Culture	0.725	0.474	0.626	0.462	0.79	0.812	0.851

Structural model was used to observe the connection between various constructs. The structural model can provide an estimate of the relative strength of the hypothesized relationships by estimating path coefficients between the independent as well as dependent constructs (Hair Jr et al., 2016; Hair Jr et al., 2021). Researchers can assess whether the independent constructs provide predictive power to the dependent constructs through an examination of path coefficients and their corresponding significance level (p-value). In addition, the R² statistic provides an indication of the

amount of variance in the dependent constructs that are described by the independent constructs. The bootstrapping method allows for the examination of the statistical significance (t-value and p-value) of each of the paths between the constructs (Hair Jr et al., 2022; Hair Jr et al., 2017). By estimating the hypothesized paths using PLS regression, researchers can evaluate the predictive power of the proposed causal relationships and determine whether they are supported by the data collected.

Figure 2: PLS Structural Model

The results indicate that **digital culture** has a strong and significant positive influence on **employee behavior** ($\beta = 0.593, p = 0.000$). **Digital leadership** also has a very strong and significant influence on **firm performance** ($\beta = 0.946, p = 0.000$). **Employee behavior** significantly contributes to **firm performance**, though the effect is modest ($\beta = 0.055, p = 0.001$). Therefore, **digital culture has a positive effect on employee behavior, similarly, digital leadership has a positive effect on firm performance.** Regarding cultural dimensions, **goals culture** ($\beta =$

$0.052, p = 0.001$) and **norms culture** ($\beta = 0.483, p = 0.000$) significantly enhance **employee behavior**. However, **innovation culture** does not show a statistically significant impact ($\beta = 0.079, p = 0.129$). Furthermore, the **moderating influence** is significant ($\beta = 0.043, p = 0.040$), suggesting that the interaction term meaningfully influences **firm performance**. The moderation effect results are explained through Figure 3 which shows that digital leadership strengthens the relationship between employee behavior and firm performance.

Table 4: Path Coefficient Results

	β	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Digital Culture -> Employee Behavior	0.593	0.054	11.071	0
Digital Leadership -> Firm Performance	0.946	0.018	51.5	0
Employee Behavior -> Firm Performance	0.055	0.016	3.425	0.001
Goals Culture -> Employee Behavior	0.052	0.016	3.245	0.001
Innovation Culture -> Employee Behavior	0.079	0.052	1.521	0.129
Moderating Effect 1 -> Firm Performance	0.043	0.021	2.061	0.04
Norms Culture -> Employee Behavior	0.483	0.065	7.475	0

Figure 3: Moderation Effect

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to examine the influence of cultural values archetypes on firm performance through employee behavior in SMEs. **This objective was addressed by examining the relationship between** cultural value archetypes such as innovation culture, goals culture, norms culture and digital culture along with employee behavior, digital leadership and firm performance. This relationship was examined through seven hypotheses including six direct effect hypotheses and one moderation effect. Results of the study supported six hypotheses, and one hypothesis was not supported.

The findings of this study provide constructive insights into the role of cultural value archetypes, employee behavior, and digital leadership in enhancing firm performance in SMEs. Hypothesis 1, which proposed a positive relationship between innovation culture and employee behavior, was not supported in this study. These outcomes are not consistent with prior studies highlighting the positive relationship between innovative culture and employee behavior (Bindel Sibassaha et al., 2025; Li & Liu, 2022; Lukes & Stephan, 2017). This unexpected result may be attributed to the contextual characteristics of SMEs, where limited resources, informal processes, and operational pressures may hinder the translation of innovation-oriented values into actual employee behavior. Innovation culture is

supposed to help organizations to be more creative and proactive (Bindel Sibassaha et al., 2025; Lukes & Stephan, 2017; Ur Rehman et al., 2019); however, SMEs do not have the appropriate infrastructure, training, or incentives in place to keep their employees engaged in implementing new ideas effectively with the organization. As well, employees in SMEs are likely to spend much more time and energy focusing on operating everyday tasks than they do on experimenting with new processes. This behavior reduces the observable impact that an innovative culture has on individual behaviors within SMEs.

Hypothesis 2, which posited a positive connection between goals culture and employee behavior, was supported. The findings indicate that when SMEs establish clear objectives and communicate expected outcomes, employees tend to demonstrate more constructive and aligned behaviors. In SMEs, where all of the employees contributions are very visible (Wang et al., 2018), methods to find direction toward their work are critical. Therefore, having employees on the same page regarding their responsibilities gives them the opportunity to coordinate their daily tasks and activities with the overall priorities of company. Similarly, previous studies reported the positive relationship between goal culture and employee behavior (Nwugwo, 2001; Santos et al., 2012). Furthermore, hypothesis 3, which predicted a

positive relationship between norms culture and employee behavior, was also supported. As similar behavioral expectations, ethical standards, and organizational norms define how employees should behave, employees will likely be encouraged to support and engage in cooperative, responsible, and performance-oriented behaviors. SMEs can benefit from the visibility of their norms (Caniëls et al., 2015) by communicating their norms clearly, SMEs promote coordination, lower uncertainty, and enhance the ability to develop mutual understanding between employees. This result supports earlier research that has shown that organizations with strong normative frameworks can shape employee habitual behaviors, which creates efficient organizations. This is especially true for small-sized organizations, in which informal relationships play a huge part in daily operations of organizations. Also, other studies have consistently reported the beneficial impact of norms culture on employee behavior (Choi & Lee, 2017; Orpen, 1993; Whitson et al., 2015). Hypothesis 4, examining the positive relationship between digital culture and employee behavior, was supported as well. The employees working in such a workplace develop the skills to use digital resources to increase their productivity when it comes to solving the typical problem, establishing collaboration with coworkers, and responding to future opportunities. The importance of digitalizing is evident by the significance that SMEs will have on digital culture; thus, encouraging the culture of support for technology within SMEs. Consistent with this study, findings highlighted the positive relationship between digital culture and employee behavior (Al-Romeedy, 2024; Cetinkaya & Surucu, 2025).

Hypothesis 5, which proposed a positive relationship between employee behavior and firm performance, was supported. Employees proactive, responsible, and collaborative behaviors were found to significantly contribute to organizational outcomes in SMEs. This finding provides additional support for the dynamic capabilities viewpoint where employees serve as micro-level carriers of firm level organizational capabilities and thus help to convert an organization's intangible (i.e., cultural) and tangible (i.e., structural) resources into the highest level of measurable business performance. It also demonstrates that SMEs can improve the business performance of their firms through the development of positive behavior of employees (Khan et al., 2024; Li & Liu, 2022; Utomo et al., 2023), given the relatively small size and high reliance on employee knowledge that characterizes SMEs.

Hypothesis 6, predicting a positive connection between digital leadership and firm performance,

was supported. This result is consistent with prior research suggesting that leaders who possess digital vision and competence can strategically leverage technology to enhance firm-level outcomes (Hung et al., 2023; Norouzi et al., 2022). Finally, hypothesis 7, which proposed that digital leadership positively moderates the relationship between employee behavior and firm performance, was supported. Through understanding these findings, it has been indicated that positive employee behaviors have a greater influence on corporate performance under conditions where there is effective digital leadership. Digital leaders create further facilitation by way of augmenting the effects of constructive employee behaviors through their provision of the appropriate resources, guidance, and information technology infrastructure for employees to be able to perform better.

In conclusion, this study highlights the critical role of cultural values, employee behavior, and digital leadership in driving firm performance in SMEs. Research findings indicate that innovative-oriented cultures have an indirect effect on employee behavior. Conversely, cultures focused on goal setting, normative behavior and technology directly promote employee participation in positive constructive behavior. Therefore, employee positive behavior has a direct impact on the performance of an organization. Additionally, the behavior of employees supports and amplifies the positive influence of employee behavior on profitability, allowed by digital leadership. Collectively, these findings highlight that in order to fully optimize employee performance organizations must create a culture with aligned values and develop digital leaders. In summary, the information provided in the study could be of assistance to SMEs wanting to achieve sustainable and competitive growth.

5.1. Theoretical Implications

The current study has valuable contribution to the body of knowledge leading to important theoretical implications. This study extends DCT by demonstrating how cultural value archetypes function as internal capabilities that shape employee behavior, a micro-level mechanism influencing firm performance in SMEs. The study also emphasizes the significance of developing a goal-driven culture within small businesses since clear objectives significantly influence employee performance, thus completing the existing literature on organizational behaviors. By confirming that normative culture serves as a source of stability for small enterprises by establishing common expectations and standards for behavior. Therefore, this research finds that such established behaviors, support employee ability to

perform well within a small business setting. Additionally, this study finds that organizations can leverage their employees through the establishment of a technology-enabled workplace culture by incorporating digital-based resources into the workplace. In contrast, the findings highlight that innovation culture has no statistically significant effect on employee behavior among SMEs, which is a doubt on the assumptions made in large company studies and underscores the need to develop theories specific to the context of innovation implementation. Moreover, supporting the role of leadership in enhancing the impact of human capital, digital leadership acts as a moderating factor between digital leadership and innovation culture-enhancing human capital and aligns with an extension of strategic management literature on leadership in dynamic settings. Collectively, these findings advance the theoretical integration of culture and leadership and develop a methodological framework for future SME-focused studies on performance.

5.2. Practical Implications

The contribution of this study provided important implications for the policymakers. SME managers should cultivate goals culture by setting clear objectives and communicating expectations to align employee behavior with organizational priorities. Based on the results of the study, practitioners should promote a culture of normative behavior as this will encourage ethical, responsible, and cooperative conduct and will also help to improve the level of coordination and performance overall. In addition, practitioners should encourage a digital culture for employees to assist with their adjustment to technological shifts, thereby enhancing productivity and innovation in SMEs. While an Innovation-Based Culture is important for the generation of innovative ideas in SMEs, managers must also provide the necessary resources and support in order to effectively execute those innovative ideas. It is recommended that digital leadership should be strengthened to guide employees in adopting technology and executing digital initiatives efficiently. SMEs can leverage employee behavior as a key driver of performance, emphasizing recognition and reward systems for proactive actions. Finally, findings provide a blueprint for SMEs to align culture, behavior, and leadership strategically, promoting sustainable growth and competitive advantage.

6. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This study extends the body of knowledge by examining the relationship between cultural value archetypes such as innovation culture, goals culture,

norms culture and digital culture along with employee behavior and firm performance. However, this study has few limitations which can be used as future directions for future studies. This study was conducted only in SMEs, which may limit the **generalizability** of findings to larger organizations or different industries. Future studies should address various other companies based on large scale. Innovation culture was not found significant; **contextual factors** such as resource constraints in SMEs were not fully explored which can be considered by the previous studies. In this study, cultural archetypes were limited to innovation, goals, norms, and digital culture; other cultural dimensions may also influence employee behavior. Hence, future studies should consider various other dimensions of cultural archetypes. Finally, this research did not examine **industry-specific differences** that might moderate the relationships studied. Hence, future studies should consider **industry-specific differences for better originality of results**.

7. FUNDING

This work was supported by the Deanship of Scientific Research, Vice Presidency for Graduate Studies and Scientific Research, King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia [Grant Number: KFU254557].

REFERENCES

- Ababneh, O. M. A. (2021). The impact of organizational culture archetypes on quality performance and total quality management: the role of employee engagement and individual values. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 38(6), 1387-1408. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-05-2020-0178>
- Al-Romeedy, B. S. (2024). HRM and Digital Leadership: Exploring the Mediating Role of Digital Talent and Digital Culture in Driving Innovative Performance in Saudi Arabia's Tourism and Hospitality Industry. In O. D. Adekoya, C. Mordi, & H. A. Ajonbadi (Eds.), *HRM, Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Work: Insights from the Global South* (pp. 101-123). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-62369-1_6
- Al Koliby, I. S., Mehat, N. A. B., Al-Swidi, A. K., & Al-Hakimi, M. A. (2024). Unveiling the linkages between entrepreneurial culture, innovation capability, digital marketing capability and sustainable competitive performance of manufacturing SMEs: evidence from emerging countries. *The Bottom Line*, 37(4), 473-500. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BL-08-2023-0241>
- Anis, L., Perez, G., Benzie, K. M., Ewashen, C., Hart, M., & Letourneau, N. (2020). Convergent validity of three measures of reflective function: Parent development interview, parental reflective function questionnaire, and reflective function questionnaire. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 574719. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BL-08-2023-0241>
- Artüz, S. D., & Bayraktar, O. (2021). The effect of relation between digital leadership practice and learning organization on the perception of individual performance [Dijital liderlik uygulaması ile Öğrenen Örgüt İlişkisinin bireysel performansına etkisi]. *İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 20(40), 97-120. <https://doi.org/10.46928/iticusbe.761479>
- Benitez, J., Arenas, A., Castillo, A., & Esteves, J. (2022). Impact of digital leadership capability on innovation performance: The role of platform digitization capability. *Information & Management*, 59(2), 103590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2022.103590>
- Bienkowska, A., & Tworek, K. (2020). Job Performance Model Based on Employees' Dynamic Capabilities (EDC). *Sustainability*, 12(6), 2250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12062250>
- Bindel Sibassaha, J. L., Pea-Assounga, J. B. B., & Bambi, P. D. R. (2025). Influence of digital transformation on employee innovative behavior: roles of challenging appraisal, organizational culture support, and transformational leadership style. *Frontiers in psychology*, 16, 1532977. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1532977>
- Cabrero, J. D. B., Sanmartín, M. C., & Segura, L. R. (2021). Digital skills as a vehicle for university organizational culture. *Revista Latina de Comunicación Social*(79), 17-33. <https://doi.org/10.4185/RLCS-2021-1495>
- Caniëls, M. C., Lenaerts, H. K., & Gelderman, C. J. (2015). Explaining the internet usage of SMEs: The impact of market orientation, behavioural norms, motivation and technology acceptance. *Internet Research*, 25(3), 358-377. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-12-2013-0266>
- Canning, E. A., Murphy, M. C., Emerson, K. T., Chatman, J. A., Dweck, C. S., & Kray, L. J. (2020). Cultures of genius at work: Organizational mindsets predict cultural norms, trust, and commitment. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 46(4), 626-642.
- Cetinkaya, B., & Surucu, L. (2025). The Influence of Digital Culture and Digital Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior. *Studies in Media and Communication*, 13(3), 236-247. <https://doi.org/10.11114/smc.v13i3.7709>
- Cheah, J.-H., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Ramayah, T., & Ting, H. (2018). Convergent validity assessment of formatively measured constructs in PLS-SEM: On using single-item versus multi-item measures in redundancy analyses. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management*, 30(11), 3192-3210. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-10-2017-0649>
- Cherian, J., Gaikar, V., Paul, R., & Pech, R. (2021). Corporate Culture and Its Impact on Employees' Attitude, Performance, Productivity, and Behavior: An Investigative Analysis from Selected Organizations of the United Arab Emirates (UAE). *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7010045>
- Chlpeková, A., Večera, P., & Šurinová, Y. (2014). Enhancing the Effectiveness of Problem-Solving Processes through Employee Motivation and Involvement. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, 6, 31. <https://doi.org/10.5772/59431>
- Choi, B., & Lee, S. (2017). Role of Social Norms and Social Identifications in Safety Behavior of Construction Workers. II: Group Analyses for the Effects of Cultural Backgrounds and Organizational Structures on Social Influence Process. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 143(5), 04016125. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0001254](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001254)

- Delmotte, J., Maes, J., Faems, D., Forrier, A., & Sels, L. (2006). Linking Hrm and Small Business Performance: An Examination of the Impact of Hrm Intensity on the Productivity and Financial Performance of Small Businesses. *Small Business Economics*, 26(1), 83-101.
- Fabbri, T., Mandreoli, F., Martoglia, R., & Scapolan, A. C. (2019). Employee attitudes and (digital) collaboration data: A preliminary analysis in the HRM field. 2019 28th International Conference on Computer Communication and Networks (ICCCN),
- Gao, P., & Gao, Y. (2024). How Does Digital Leadership Foster Employee Innovative Behavior: A Cognitive-Affective Processing System Perspective. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(5), 362. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs14050362>
- García-Fernández, J., Martelo-Landroguez, S., Vélez-Colon, L., & Cepeda-Carrión, G. (2018). An explanatory and predictive PLS-SEM approach to the relationship between organizational culture, organizational performance and customer loyalty: The case of health clubs. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 9(3), 438-454. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTT-09-2017-0100>
- Gherghina, Ș. C., Botezatu, M. A., Hosszu, A., & Simionescu, L. N. (2020). Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs): The Engine of Economic Growth through Investments and Innovation. *Sustainability*, 12(1), 347. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12010347>
- Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Pieper, T. M., & Ringle, C. M. (2012). The Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Strategic Management Research: A Review of Past Practices and Recommendations for Future Applications. *Long Range Planning*, 45(5), 320-340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2012.09.008>
- Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). Sage Publications. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acclit.2016.09.003>
- Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R: A workbook. Springer Nature. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80519-7>
- Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2022). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R: A workbook. Springer Nature.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Matthews, L. M., Matthews, R. L., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). PLS-SEM or CB-SEM: updated guidelines on which method to use. *International Journal of Multivariate Data Analysis*, 1(2), 107-123. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMDA.2017.087624>
- Henseler, J., Dijkstra, T. K., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Diamantopoulos, A., Straub, D. W., Ketchen Jr, D. J., Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., & Calantone, R. J. (2014). Common beliefs and reality about PLS: Comments on Rönkkö and Evermann (2013). *Organizational Research Methods*, 17(2), 182-209. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428114526928>
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing. In *New challenges to international marketing* (pp. 277-319). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979\(2009\)0000020014](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979(2009)0000020014)
- Hilkenmeier, F., Bohndick, C., Bohndick, T., & Hilkenmeier, J. (2020). Assessing distinctiveness in multidimensional instruments without access to raw data—a manifest Fornell-Larcker criterion. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 223. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00223>
- Hung, B. Q., Hoa, T. A., Hoai, T. T., & Nguyen, N. P. (2023). Advancement of cloud-based accounting effectiveness, decision-making quality, and firm performance through digital transformation and digital leadership: Empirical evidence from Vietnam. *Heliyon*, 9(6). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16929>
- Iqbal, J., & Parray, Z. A. (2025). Striking the balance: unraveling the influence of organizational culture on organization citizenship behavior with corporate social responsibility as the bridge. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 74(6), 2091-2112. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-01-2024-0065>
- Isac, N., Dobrin, C., Raphalalani, L. P., & Sonko, M. (2021). Does organizational culture influence job satisfaction? A comparative analysis of two multinational companies. *Revista de Management Comparat International*, 22(2), 138-157. <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=1047326>
- Januszkiewicz, K. (2022). Understanding flexibility—dimensions of employee behavior flexibility. *International Journal of Contemporary Management*, 58(3). <https://doi.org/10.2478/ijcm-2022-0003>
- Joo, B.-K. B., & Bennett III, R. H. (2018). The influence of proactivity on creative behavior, organizational commitment, and job performance: evidence from a Korean multinational. *Journal of International & Interdisciplinary Business Research* (2014-2019), 5(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.58809/GWXR1454>
- Joo, J., Kim, D., Song, J. H., & Yoo, M. (2025). Is career development resource always perceived good in SMEs?

- A comparative analysis of employment. *European Journal of Training and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-07-2024-0098>
- Khan, S. A. R., Sheikh, A. A., & Tahir, M. S. (2024). Corporate social responsibility – an antidote for sustainable business performance: interconnecting role of digital technologies, employee eco-behavior, and tax avoidance. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31(3), 4365-4383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-31377-9>
- Kharub, M., Mondal, S., Singh, S., & Gupta, H. (2025). Evaluation of competency dimensions for employee performance assessment: evidence from micro, small, and medium enterprises. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 74(1), 107-138. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-07-2023-0379>
- Khaw, T. Y., Ping, T., Siti-Nabiha, A. K., & Letchmunan, S. (2022). The impact of digital leadership on sustainable performance: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Management Development*, 41(4). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMD-03-2022-0070>
- Kmecová, I., & Androniceanu, A. (2024). Level of investments in human capital in SMEs as a means of further development and increased competitiveness. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 16(1), 79. <https://doi.org/10.7441/joc.2024.01.05>
- Lamberti, G., Lopez-Sintas, J., & Katz-Gerro, T. (2025). Access to digital culture as a driver of social and cultural openness: European evidence. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1), 180. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-04091-1>
- Lau, P. Y. Y., Tong, J. L. Y. T., Lien, B. Y.-H., Hsu, Y.-C., & Chong, C. L. (2017). Ethical work climate, employee commitment and proactive customer service performance: Test of the mediating effects of organizational politics. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 35, 20-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2016.11.004>
- Leal-Rodríguez, A. L., Sanchís-Pedregosa, C., Moreno-Moreno, A. M., & Leal-Millán, A. G. (2023). Digitalization beyond technology: Proposing an explanatory and predictive model for digital culture in organizations. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 8(3), 100409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2023.100409>
- Li, Z., & Liu, L. (2022). The impact of organizational innovation culture on employees' innovation behavior. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 50(12), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.11934>
- Liu, J. Y., Shiue, W., Chen, F. H., & Huang, A. T. (2019). A multiple attribute decision making approach in evaluating employee care strategies of corporate social responsibility. *Management Decision*, 57(2), 349-371. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-03-2018-0230>
- Lukes, M., & Stephan, U. (2017). Measuring employee innovation: A review of existing scales and the development of the innovative behavior and innovation support inventories across cultures. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 23(1), 136-158. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBr-11-2015-0262>
- Meng, B., Lee, M. J., Chua, B.-L., & Han, H. (2022). An integrated framework of behavioral reasoning theory, theory of planned behavior, moral norm and emotions for fostering hospitality/tourism employees' sustainable behaviors. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management*, 34(12), 4516-4538. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-02-2022-0151>
- Mihelj, S., Leguina, A., & Downey, J. (2019). Culture is digital: Cultural participation, diversity and the digital divide. *New Media & Society*, 21(7), 1465-1485. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818822816>
- Mikic Little, M., & Dean, A. M. (2006). Links between service climate, employee commitment and employees' service quality capability. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 16(5), 460-476. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520610686133>
- Norouzi, H., Nosrat Panah, R., & Barani, S. (2022). The influence of digital leadership on firm performance in dynamic environments: The role of dynamic capabilities, business model innovation, and sustainable competitive advantage. *Journal of Business Management*, 14(3), 445-474. <https://doi.org/10.22059/jibm.2022.333405.4290>
- Nwugwo, B. C. (2001). The impact of organizational culture on employee behavior and attitude. *Running head*, 2, 1-34. http://www.btctechnologies.com/boni/od501_paper.pdf
- Orpen, C. (1993). The Effect of Organizational Cultural Norms on the Relationships Between Personnel Practices and Employee Commitment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 127(5), 577-579. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1993.9914896>
- Oude Mulders, J., Henkens, K., & Schippers, J. (2017). European top managers' age-related workplace norms and their organizations' recruitment and retention practices regarding older workers. *The Gerontologist*, 57(5), 857-866. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnw076>

- Proksch, D., Rosin, A. F., Stubner, S., & Pinkwart, A. (2024). The influence of a digital strategy on the digitalization of new ventures: The mediating effect of digital capabilities and a digital culture. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 62(1), 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00472778.2021.1883036>
- Putthiwanit, C. (2015). Exploring the Impact of Organizational Culture on Employees in Multinational Enterprise: A Qualitative Approach. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 207, 483-491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.10.118>
- Rab, Á. (2007). Digital culture–Digitalised culture and culture created on a digital platform. *Information Society From Theory to Political Practice*, 183, 1-24. https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/114476624/11_Rab_final-libre.pdf?1715578721=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DPDF_Digital_culture_Mi_az_ITTK.pdf&Expires=1765681247&Signature=KijAldmJ08evwkLMVVuIePb4fPzrZ~EPz9-17My~PfrVzS~9sQ8z2Y1Av2IuHOP6UyofF3zHbiToUqID3hSboUJYSJyqAkiN8cUdoJASAFuyeeSmTqQG329Ix2JL6hMfHOX0~g0TVJ9vVkrmiH~9rjHsTerRerEyT5NcCAD0EevjAWKgRU~RUa05yfPKwUhj8VLt8HVFLAz8l3QsHGvtI7C4CiKYkmzY0QBdYYUivUmiqFZws5kulQeQLM3APYlzWwoAYHLKsOModUSjaAlaE-EEPC95IUChNzq0MU~DZCo5r8U4ieiEDcmLMVh8BCcZt2qrQ1DmElv15HiCSm4w__&Key-Pair-Id=APKAJLOHF5GGSLRBV4ZA
- Santos, A., Hayward, T., & Ramos, H. M. (2012). Organizational culture, work and personal goals as predictors of employee well-being. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communication and Conflict*, 16(1), 25-48. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hazel_Melanie_Ramos/publication/285953933_Organizational_culture_work_and_personal_goals_as_predictors_of_employee_well-being/links/578de90708ae35e97c3f4658.pdf
- Sharif, S., Lodhi, R. N., Jain, V., & Sharma, P. (2022). A dark side of land revenue management and counterproductive work behavior: Does organizational injustice add fuel to fire? *Journal of Public Procurement*, 22(4), 265-288. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOPP-10-2021-0062>
- Shin, J., Mollah, M. A., & Choi, J. (2023). Sustainability and Organizational Performance in South Korea: The Effect of Digital Leadership on Digital Culture and Employees' Digital Capabilities. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2027. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032027>
- Suharto, S., & Nusantoro, J. (2018). The Relationship Among Managerial Capability, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, And Employee Performance: Mediation Effects Of Organizational Culture. *Journal of Community Research and Service*, 2(1), 168-175. <https://doi.org/10.24114/jcrs.v2i1.9890>
- Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic management journal*, 18(7), 509-533. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0266\(199708\)18:7%3C509::AID-SMJ882%3E3.0.CO;2-Z](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199708)18:7%3C509::AID-SMJ882%3E3.0.CO;2-Z)
- Ur Rehman, S., Bhatti, A., & Chaudhry, N. I. (2019). Mediating effect of innovative culture and organizational learning between leadership styles at third-order and organizational performance in Malaysian SMEs. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 9(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40497-019-0159-1>
- Utomo, H. J. N., Irwantoro, I., Wasesa, S., Purwati, T., Sembiring, R., & Purwanto, A. (2023). Investigating the role of innovative work behavior, organizational trust, perceived organizational support: an empirical study on SMEs performance. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 11(2), e417-e417. <https://doi.org/10.55908/sdgs.v11i2.417>
- Wang, T., Thornhill, S., & Zhao, B. (2018). Pay-for-performance, employee participation, and SME performance. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56(3), 412-434. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsbm.12268>
- Whitson, J., Wang, C. S., Kim, J., Cao, J., & Scrimshire, A. (2015). Responses to normative and norm-violating behavior: Culture, job mobility, and social inclusion and exclusion. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 129, 24-35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2014.08.001>
- Wijaya, I., Rahardjo, K., Abdillah, Y., & Riza, M. F. (2025). Sustainability performance in business: a systematic review of leadership, culture, capability and digital marketing contributions. *Cogent Business & Management*, 12(1), 2543049. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2025.2543049>
- Wijaya, I. G. N. S., Pratami, N. W. C. A., Yudiastira, P. P., & Arista, M. Y. (2019). The Impact between the Use of Information Technology, User Ability on User Motivation and Employee Performance in the Koperasi Kuta Mimba. 2019 1st International Conference on Cybernetics and Intelligent System (ICORIS),
- Xiufan, Z., & Yunqiao, L. L. (2025). CIO leadership, employee digital ability, and corporate green innovation performance—moderating effect of organizational agility and environmental culture. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 27(10), 24585-24628. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-024-05581-7>
- Yang, M., Talha, M., Zhang, S., & Zhang, Y. (2025). Exploring the Mechanisms Linking Digital Leadership to

- Employee Creativity: A Moderated Mediation Model. *Behavioral Sciences*, 15(8), 1024. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs15081024>
- Youssef, A. A., & ElSabry, E. A. (2025). The Challenge of Innovation Measurement in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs): Approaches and Challenges in Assessing Innovative Capabilities. *Interdisciplinary Studies on Digital Transformation and Innovation: Business, Education, and Medical Approaches*, 99-126. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3373-1132-6.ch004>
- Zhang, L., Xu, Y., Chen, C., & Zhao, R. (2022). Predicting the factors of employee agility using enterprise social media: The moderating role of innovation culture. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 911427. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.911427>
- Zheng, W., Wu, Y.-C. J., Chen, X., & Lin, S.-J. (2017). Why do employees have counterproductive work behavior? The role of founder's Machiavellianism and the corporate culture in China. *Management Decision*, 55(3), 563-578. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-10-2016-0696>
- Zotoo, I. K., Lu, Z., & Liu, G. (2021). Big data management capabilities and librarians' innovative performance: The role of value perception using the theory of knowledge-based dynamic capability. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 47(2), 102272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2020.102272>